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Enabling shared perceptions between Virtual and Augmented Reality users

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Declaration of authorship

I hereby confirm that this thesis is entirely my own original work. All parts of this thesis that are taken from other works, either in words or in meaning, have been marked as such and are listed as references. This thesis has not been submitted to any other examination board and has not been published.

Ralf Strecker

Berlin, 2023-08-28

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Abbreviations

AR	Augmented reality
VR	Virtual reality
MR	Mixed reality
SWIS	See what I see (title of the developed prototype application)
HL1	Microsoft HoloLens (AR headset)
HL2	Microsoft HoloLens 2 (AR headset)
MQ2	Meta Quest 2 (VR headset)
MRTK3	Mixed Reality Toolkit 3 (MR interaction toolkit)
GUID	Globally unique identifier
fps	Frames per second (frequency of an event in Hertz)

Abstract

English

This thesis provides insight into a novel mode of communication by combining augmented and virtual reality. The author presents "See what I see", an application prototype that can be used to share the physical environment of an AR user with one or more remotely located VR users. The local and remote user(s) are visualized as virtual avatars and can interact with each other in real-time through hand gestures and spatial annotations. The application has been evaluated technically and was found to perform well in real-time with bi-directional data rates between 400 and 500 $\frac{\text{KB}}{\text{s}}$. Furthermore, user tests have been conducted and participants reported a sense of togetherness and feeling present in the shared physical-virtual space. While specific use cases are discussed, this work is intended more as a general exploration of the technological capabilities.

Deutsch

Ziel dieser Arbeit ist es, eine neuartige Form der Kommunikation zu untersuchen, in der eine Mischung aus Augmented und Virtual Reality verwendet wird. Der Autor präsentiert die Anwendung "See what I see", einen Anwendungsprototypen, der dazu verwendet werden kann, die physische Umgebung einer Person in AR mit einer oder mehreren räumlich entfernten Personen in VR zu teilen. Die lokal anwesende Person und die entfernte(n) Person(en) werden einander als virtuelle Avatare visualisiert und können in Echtzeit durch Handgesten und räumliche Annotationen miteinander interagieren. Die Anwendung wurde einer technischen Bewertung unterzogen und erwies sich als leistungsfähig in Echtzeit, mit bidirektionalen Datenraten zwischen 400 und 500 $\frac{\text{KB}}{\text{s}}$. Zusätzlich wurden Nutzungstests durchgeführt, bei welchen die Teilnehmenden von einem Gefühl des Gemeinsamseins und der Präsenz in der Umgebung berichteten, welches durch das gemeinsame Beleben eines physisch-virtuellen Raumes ermöglicht wurde. Obwohl spezifische Anwendungsfälle diskutiert werden, stellt diese Arbeit eher eine allgemeine Erkundung der technologischen Möglichkeiten dar.

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Telecommunications between people have become increasingly immersive over time. With a phone call, people could talk to each other as if they were standing next to one another. Video telephony allowed people to see each other and show the environment they were in and experience it together. Virtual reality enabled seeing each other as avatars and thus communicate spatially. Augmented reality made it possible to combine the virtual and physical worlds by projecting virtual objects into the real environment. An ever increasing number of aspects can be shared during communication, making the experience more and more immersive and informative. Using AR and VR technology, how can the level of immersion be further increased? To allow a remote user to perceive a local user's environment, one relatively simple option would be to transmit a video stream captured by an AR headset. The remote user's point of view would, however, always be identical to the AR user's, similar to regular video telephony. For independent exploration of the environment and a deeper sense of immersion, the remote user would need access to a comprehensive scan of the environment. While this scan could be conducted ahead of time with mapping hardware such as a terrestrial laser scanner, it would be time-consuming and not very convenient.

That is the idea on which this thesis is built: An AR headset's mapping capabilities can be used to perform a scan of the environment and send it to the remote VR user. The scan can be updated continuously, so changes in the physical world are mirrored in the virtual scan after a short while. Both users can see each other and can jointly inhabit the AR user's physical environment.

1.2 Objective

A prototype application named "See what I see" – hereafter SWIS – was developed as part of this thesis. The goal was to explore the feasibility and technological capabilities of the approach outlined above, so the application was not developed towards a specific use case but rather as a broad tool to evaluate and demonstrate the general technology. The thesis aims to find answers to the following questions:

- How can a system be created that enables a remote VR user to perceive the physical environment in which an AR user is situated?
- How can communication between users and shared spatial awareness be established?
- How does such a system perform technically and how do users assess the experience subjectively?
- For what use cases would such a system be applicable?

The thesis intends to answer these questions by providing insight into the development, conducting demonstrations of the technology with participants and evaluate their feedback, as well as testing the application for performance indicators. While individual components of the application, such as the spatial mapping capability and avatar visualization, have already been examined, the combination, in particular the continuous transmission of the environment scan, has been less studied and will hopefully advance the field.

1.3 Technology

The implementation of the prototype requires hardware that supports the necessary functionalities of environment scanning and hand tracking. In the following, the most common hardware options are described, and a reasoned selection is made.

Although most 6 DoF (degrees of freedom) AR headsets are equipped with sensors for spatially mapping their environment, not all of them offer easy access to these scan data. At the time of writing, the most established option is Microsoft HoloLens 2 [1]. Magic Leap 2 [2] also fulfills all of the technical requirements; however, after preliminary research, it appears to be less studied than HoloLens 2. There are other promising options such as Lynx R1 [3] and Apple Vision Pro [4], but both are not yet generally available. HoloLens 2 – hereafter HL2 – was chosen for the AR part of the application because of its convenient access to the spatial mapping data, good documentation, availability, and the author’s familiarity with it. The environment mapping capabilities and limitations of HL2 have already been evaluated by the author in a previous term paper.

The VR part of the application does not call for special hardware requirements, except for hand tracking. Even if hand tracking is not integrated, it could be added with

additional sensors such as Leap Motion [5]. Therefore, any VR headset with 6 DoF tracking would fulfill the requirements. There are, however, several headsets with integrated hand tracking available, which would limit external dependencies. Another consideration is ease of use: While some (mostly wired) VR headsets require an external computer, others can operate standalone. Furthermore, some VR headsets require external tracking hardware, while others use inside-out tracking, similar to AR headsets, and are therefore more portable. Options that meet all these requirements include Meta Quest 2 [6], Meta Quest Pro [7] and HTC VIVE Focus 3 [8]. Meta Quest 2 – hereafter MQ2 – was chosen for the VR part of the application because of its ability to operate standalone (without an external computer), integrated hand-tracking, availability, and the author’s familiarity with it.

The following sections describe the specifications and limitations of the selected hardware options.

Figure 1: Mixed reality headsets

1.3.1 Microsoft HoloLens 2

HoloLens 2 uses a holographic see-through display to overlay virtual content onto the real world. It is equipped with 4 visible light cameras, a 1 megapixel Time-of-Flight depth sensor and an inertial measurement unit comprising an accelerometer, a gyroscope, and a magnetometer [1]. All of these sensors combined enable the headset to perform visual-inertial SLAM (simultaneous localization and mapping) and 6 DoF tracking. The headset runs Windows Holographic OS (based on Windows 10) on a Qualcomm Snapdragon 850 processor, enabling the headset to run applications standalone.

Limitations

Scanning the environment comes with certain limitations, which the author examined in a previous term paper. Since HL2 uses visible light cameras as its primary input of localization, the environment must be evenly lit: "When an environment is too bright, the cameras can get saturated, and nothing is seen. If the environment is too dark, the cameras can't pick up enough information, and nothing is seen. Lighting should be even and sufficiently bright a human can see without effort, but not so bright the light is painful to look at." [9] Another problem is large uniform areas, such as unicolored walls. When the headset can't register discernible visual features, it can't locate itself. Furthermore, the depth sensor uses reflected infrared light to measure depth, so materials that absorb in that spectrum will not be registered, which can lead to holes and missing parts in the scanned mesh.

HL2's displays offer a relatively low field of view with 43° horizontal and 29° vertical [10]. As an average human's field of view of 145° horizontal and 100° vertical (per eye) is much larger, the virtual content can only be overlaid on a small portion of a user's view [11].

Furthermore, hand tracking is performed visually from the headset's position. Therefore, the hands can only be tracked in a limited frustum determined by where a user looks.

1.3.2 Meta Quest 2

Meta Quest 2 uses an opaque display to display fully immersive virtual content. It uses inside-out tracking, enabling 6 DoF tracking. It runs a custom Android-based operating system on a Qualcomm Snapdragon XR2 processor, allowing standalone operation. The headset can be used either with VR controllers or with hand tracking.

Limitations

Same as with HL2, the hand tracking will only work in a limited frustum originating from the user's viewing direction.

1.4 Outline

This section has given an overview of the objectives and goals pertaining to this thesis and the proposed prototype application. Relevant concepts and related work will be covered in **section 2**. In **section 3**, the development approach and methodology for measuring and evaluating the application will be introduced. Each step of the iterative development process, information on how different application features work, as well as the results of the measurements and user evaluations will be presented in **section 4**. Finally, in **section 5** the results are discussed and an outlook on future improvements is provided.

2 Theoretical background

2.1 Definitions

2.1.1 Mixed reality

The term “mixed reality” was coined by Milgram and Kishino in their paper “A Taxonomy of Mixed Reality Visual Displays” [12]. They devised a “virtuality continuum” (seen in **Figure 2**) to describe the different intermediate variations of what can be seen in a display. The scale ranges from reality, with “[...] environments consisting solely of real objects [...]” (such as when looking at a screen with a camera feed of a real-world scene), to virtuality, with “[...] environments consisting solely of virtual objects [...]” (such as when looking at “[...] a conventional computer graphic simulation”). Anything between these two poles is considered mixed reality. Depending on the ratio of real and virtual content, the authors distinguish between augmented reality and augmented virtuality.

Figure 2: Reality-virtuality continuum
Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Virtuality_continuum_2-en.svg

Almost three decades later, the Microsoft Mixed Reality Team defined mixed reality as “[...] a blend of physical and digital worlds, unlocking natural and intuitive 3D human, computer, and environmental interactions.” [13] They divided spatial computing experiences into a “mixed reality spectrum” (seen in **Figure 3**), which is quite similar to the virtuality continuum. “The experiences that overlay graphics, video streams, or holograms in the physical world [...]” are considered augmented reality and “[...] experiences that occlude your view to present a fully immersive digital experience [...]” are considered virtual reality by them. Mixed Reality is defined as being formed by “[...] experiences that can transition between augmented and virtual realities [...]”.

The intention of the prototype software SWIS is to enable shared perceptions between users at different locations on this spectrum. So where can it be placed on

Figure 3: Mixed reality spectrum
 Source: <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/mixed-reality/discover/images/mixedrealityspectrum.png>

Microsoft's and Milgram and Kishino's scales? The application will run on two different head-mounted displays, HL2 and MQ2. The part running on HL2 would be considered augmented reality as defined by Milgram and Kishino, since the main visual content is the real physical environment perceived by the user through the transparent holographic display. This perceived reality is augmented by additional virtual objects, such as the avatar of the other user. Following the definition of Microsoft Mixed Reality Team, HL2 part of the application would also be regarded as augmented reality, as it overlays holograms onto the physical world.

In contrast, the part running on MQ2 can not be categorized as easily. At first glance it would seem to be far to the right on both the reality-virtuality continuum and mixed reality spectrum scales, as everything that can be seen are virtual objects and the user's view is occluded. Looking more closely, it can, however, be argued that the transmitted environment scan can be regarded as part of a real-world physical scene akin to a video stream, albeit at a much slower frame rate. Therefore, the application part on the MQ2 could similarly be regarded closer to augmented reality than it would initially seem.

For the sake of simplification and clarity, going forward in this document, the application part running on HL2 is called AR and the part running on MQ2 is called VR. The entirety of the SWIS prototype is regarded as a mixed reality application.

2.1.2 Spatial mapping

Mapping an environment requires the mapping device to have an understanding of where it is located in space so it can accurately build a map of what its sensors register [14]. Traditionally, an environment mapping device such as a terrestrial laser scanner would be set up at one or more fixed points and scan the environment from there. Mobile mapping devices, such as HL2, are, however, not fixed in space and must therefore continuously update their own position in relation to the environment. Simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) “[...] refers to techniques that solve the problem of building the map of the environment without any prior knowledge and at the same time localizing the robot [(mapping device)] into this built-map without any human interference.” [15] Data from multiple sensors such as cameras, accelerometers etc. are merged to gain an understanding of the movement of the mapping device and map its surroundings at the same time. HL2 uses real-time visual-inertial SLAM via an inertial measurement unit and four RGB cameras for localization and a long throw depth sensor for mapping [16]. While the depth sensor can capture infrared light and is thus independent from ambient lighting, the cameras used for localization can see only visible light. This means that localization and subsequently mapping precision are highly affected by the quality of ambient lighting.

2.1.3 Shared space

According to Billinghurst et al., a “Shared Space is a unique AR approach in which see-through head mounted displays allow multiple users to work in both the real and virtual world simultaneously, facilitating [computer supported collaborative work] in a seamless manner.” [17] Some approaches understand this to mean multiple co-located AR users collaborating in a shared physical space such as in the “Studierstube”, in which “[...] three-dimensional scientific data [are visualized] for multiple simultaneous viewers within one room.” [18] Other approaches understand a shared space as two or more physical spaces being connected by a shared virtual space. Gunkel et al. e.g. created a social VR experience which “[...] allows for two people to come together for mediated audiovisual interaction, while engaging in (interactive) content.” [19] Aoki et al. designed “[...] an AR-VR (Augmented Reality-Virtual Reality) connected system in which users can enter a space in which they cannot go physically

while emphasizing spatial consistency between the real and VR space.” [20] Their system was tested in an exhibition, where visitors could point a tablet at an exhibit and an augmentation would appear which could then be explored both in the physical world by walking around and entered into a completely virtual world that could be explored on the tablet screen.

For the purposes of this work, shared space means the physical space of an augmented reality user that is scanned into a digital derivative and can then be entered by one or more remotely located virtual reality users. In this way, the VR user(s) can experience a shared physically derived space with the AR user.

2.2 Related work

2.2.1 Spatial mapping

Multiple studies on the scanning capabilities of the original HoloLens – hereafter HL1 – and HL2 have been conducted: Khoshelham et al. used HL1 to scan an indoor environment of approximately 300 m² and compared the scan with data from a terrestrial laser scanner [21]. They found a relatively low “[...] mean distance of about 5 cm to the registered laser scanner point cloud [...]” which is quite good in comparison, especially as “[...] the data acquisition time was only a few minutes for the HoloLens and several hours for the laser scanner [...]”. Similarly, Hübner et al. used HL1 to map an indoor environment consisting of six rooms, compared the results with the ground truth from a terrestrial laser scanner and found an average accuracy of 2.3 cm [22]. Teruggi and Fassi evaluated the use of HL2 for mapping a very large indoor environment (parts of the Milan Cathedral) [23]. They found that the maximum effective scanning range of HL2 depth sensor was about 4 meters and therefore is not adequate for mapping vast rooms. They also found that “Deviations from reference data are negligible locally on the point of registration and increase linearly with the distance.” This means that imprecisions in the scanning increase with the dimensions of the scanned environment. Rieder et al. compared the tracking accuracy of QR codes between HL1 and HL2 and found that the precision of a tracked image was around 1mm at close range for HL2, compared to almost 2mm with HL1 [24]. This points towards better localization on HL2, compared to HL1. While the classification of scene objects such as floors, walls and ceilings had to be conducted

manually after the scanning process for HL1 [25], on HL2 it is conducted automatically in the background by Scene Understanding [26].

Another problem when working with mobile mapping devices such as HL2 is inconsistent scene alignment, as the coordinate system is initialized arbitrarily depending on HL2's pose (position and rotation) at the start of the mapping process. Hübner et al. present an approach to normalize a scene's pose according to its prevalent room geometry alignment [27]. However, this approach is not computationally fast enough to be run on HL2 in real-time scenarios. Spatial mapping devices such as HL1 or HL2 usually provide triangle meshes of the scanned environment. Triangle meshes aren't always the best option for every use case, e.g. for building information modeling (BIM). Hübner et al. presented a method to create a voxelized version of the mesh provided by HL1 in their paper "Voxel-based Indoor Reconstruction from HoloLens Triangle Meshes" [28].

An alternative approach is to not compute the spatial map directly on the device, but rather stream the sensor data to a more powerful computer and compute the scene there. This would e.g. enable implementing custom SLAM algorithms for mapping the environment. Ungureanu et al. presented a set of tools, the "HoloLens Research Mode", with which raw data from the sensors on HL2 can be directly accessed [29]. Dibene and Dunn presented a similar application which serves to stream the raw sensor data from HL2 to an external computer to leverage more computing power than available on-device on HL2 [30]. The latter method is e.g. used by Haitz et al. in their paper "Combining HoloLens with Instant-NeRFs: Advanced Real-Time 3D Mobile Mapping" [31], in which they trained a neural radiance field (a neural network used for reconstructing a 3D scene from multiple 2D images) in real-time with images and camera poses streamed from HL2 onto a powerful PC. Although this approach of external computation can deliver better scanning results, it comes at the cost of decreased end-user convenience and portability and is therefore not an option for the planned prototypical application SWIS.

2.2.2 Shared spaces & remote collaboration

Enabling a shared spatial experience between the physical world of AR and the virtual world of VR requires a common coordinate system. Benford et al. formulated the need for a "globally integrated spatial frame", which means a common spatial frame

of reference to successfully enable communication between the virtual and physical worlds, and thus create a shared space [32]. An approach demonstrated by Chun et al. is a tracking board which enables “[...] both AR and VR users to share the same physical geometric space [...]” and “[...] collaborate with each other within an integrated physical environment [...]” [33]. However, this approach does not work for remotely located users, as there is no common physical frame of reference.

Figure 4: Results from featured works

Once a common frame of reference is established, users require a way to spatially communicate their intent. According to Chastine et al., “[...] collaborators 1) need the ability to point (both physically or virtually), 2) need reference points embedded within the environment to more easily generate references, and 3) use video sharing effectively to disambiguate other communication channels for selection and reference.” [38] Gauglitz et al. developed a system using a custom SLAM implementation for Android tablets with which a remote user can annotate a physical scene [34]. The study they conducted showed that spatially anchored virtual markers were very

helpful for collaboratively solving a physical task. Müller et al. conducted a study in which they evaluated different ways of establishing common spatial reference points in a virtual environment shared by two remotely located AR users [39]. They found that shared virtual landmarks help collaborators feel connected via a shared space and improve spatial coordination.

Latency is an important metric for assessing a user's feeling of connectedness and simultaneity with the virtual world and other users within it. A study conducted by Waltermate et al. showed that latencies of up to 75 ms do not significantly impact a person's simultaneity perception when controlling a virtual avatar [40], meaning the latency to one's own avatar. Regarding the latency to other avatars, Ishii et al. found that unstable motion latency in another user's avatar was acceptable with up to even between 500 and 1500 ms as long as a simultaneous audio chat connection had a lower latency of about 33 ms [41].

Waldow and Fuhrmann presented a system for platform-independent remote mixed reality collaboration using the MQTT protocol for transmitting gesture, gaze and speech (audio) data for avatars [42]. They tested their system with two HL1 headsets and measured "[...] a throughput of ~100 Kbit/s [...] and an end-to-end network latency of ~60 ms." Waldow et al. further evaluated their system by conducting a user study for their paper "Investigating the Effect of Embodied Visualization in Remote Collaborative Augmented Reality" [37]. In the study, two participants had to solve a collaborative task under different conditions: In the blinded interaction condition, only the partners gaze was visualized, and in the avatar-mediated interaction condition, the partner's full embodied avatar was visualized. The real face-to-face condition where the partner was physically co-located was used as a baseline. They found that "[...] users feel more social presence if the partner is [...]" presented as an avatar (as opposed to only visualizing their gaze direction), but did not find significant evidence that the collaborative task could be completed faster when the partner was represented as a full avatar.

Piumsomboon et al. developed "CoVAR", a "[...] remote collaborative system combining Augmented Reality (AR), Virtual Reality (VR) and natural communication cues [...]" [36] [43]. They used a kind of "HoloLens Image-based Texturing software" to create a scan of the room with HL1. Unfortunately, at the time of writing, the linked GitHub repository is unavailable due to a DMCA takedown. Their implementation

of environment sharing was, however, not continuous, but happened only once at the beginning of a session and it had to be conducted manually by downloading the scan from HL1 and uploading it to the computer running the VR headset. The VR user could then experience the AR user's environment.

Venerella et al. proposed an approach in which "The AR mobile platform processes the live video and measures the 3D geometry of the local environment of a local user. The 3D scene is then transited [*sic*] and rendered in the remote side on a mobile VR device [...]" [35]. Their approach utilizes relatively low-cost devices, namely mobile phones. Their system "allows a remote expert to easily manipulate the 3D scene on a mobile VR platform to guide the local user to complete a complex task".

3 Methods

3.1 Requirement analysis

Looking at the related work, similar approaches to the proposed application have been attempted, but all of them have some drawbacks: The systems developed by Gauglitz et al. [34] and Venerella et al. [35] use mobile devices, such as phones or tablets and therefore require to be held with at least one hand. This approach has a reduced immersion as opposed to using an AR headset. Furthermore the users are not visualized to one another and can therefore not directly communicate spatially, but only by placing annotations. CoVAR, developed by Piumsomboon et al. [36][43], works with only a single static scan of the environment which is conducted at the start of a session. Updates in the physical environment which occur during the session are therefore not mirrored to the virtual environment.

SWIS attempts to enhance the immersion by providing avatars to enable real-time spatial communication and a continuously updating environment. The transmission of audio data to enable a voice chat is excluded from the development of the prototype, as it can be considered a solved problem. For the purpose of demonstrating the application, audio communication can be added by using an external tool (phone call or similar) in parallel to using the application. The allotted time will be spent more effectively in exploring the novel factors of environment transmission and real-time spatial communication. Following is a description of what (the first iteration of) SWIS shall provide:

The application requires two separate parts, one for AR and one for VR. In AR, a user shall be able to control the quality of the continuous scanning and transmission of their environment. The scan shall optionally be visualized as an overlay on the AR headset. The scan shall be continuously sent to the VR side. In VR, the received environment scan shall be visualized. Both AR and VR users shall see each other visualized as virtual avatars. There must exist a common frame of reference, so that the avatars are located at the correct spaces in the environment as to create a shared spatial awareness. The transmission of the avatars shall have a latency below 500 ms, preferably as low as possible, to enable real-time communication [41]. The users hands shall be tracked in both AR and VR to enable interactions with the system and to communicate with each other gesturally. Additionally, a third part for desktop is

required for debugging and testing convenience. The desktop part shall be able to receive transmitted scenes from AR and write them to disk. It shall be able to read these stored scenes and publish them to VR at a later date. Furthermore, both AR and VR avatars shall be visualized in the desktop application.

These basic specifications for the first prototype can be summarized to the following basic requirements:

1. Continuous environment scanning (*AR only*)
2. Hand and basic gesture recognition
3. Transmitting data between devices via the internet
4. Displaying meshes of both environment and transmitted avatars

The specifications of the further prototype versions can't be clearly defined at this point, as they will be developed in an iterative approach based on the evaluation of each previous version.

3.2 Approach

In order to fulfill the requirements stated above, the choice fell on Unity [44] as the 3D engine with which to develop the application. Unity is a full-fledged application development engine, which is mainly specialized in game development, but can also be utilized to create any 2D or 3D application. It provides a ready to go 3D rendering pipeline which can be used to display the meshes for both the transmitted scene as well as the avatars.

Unity also provides internal libraries for networking logic with Netcode for GameObjects [45] and the underlying low-level Transport library[46]. It is, of course, also possible to write scripts using C# to extend Unity's functionality and therefore implement any number of networking solutions.

While Unity does not directly offer implementations of hand tracking, there exist a number of third-party, mostly device-specific libraries to support hand tracking, such as Oculus Integration [47]. However, this only works for Oculus/Meta devices. Mixed Reality Toolkit 3 [48] on the other hand supports a wider range of devices, including both HL2 and MQ2. Therefore, MRTK3 was chosen to facilitate hand interactions.

Environment scanning is performed in the background on HL2 and can be accessed via the Scene Understanding SDK [26]. Its API provides access to a scene object which

contains representations of HL2's current understanding of its environment. Both MRTK3 and Scene Understanding SDK can be installed as Unity packages by Microsoft's Mixed Reality Feature Toolkit [49].

Using a single Unity project for all platforms has multiple advantages over having a separate project for each. The two most important advantages are an easily maintainable code base for common functionalities and efficient reusability of assets such as 3D models and textures. Special care must however be taken not to create conflicts between platform-specific SDKs [50].

Developing standalone software for mixed reality devices is generally more time-intensive than traditional software development due to the constant need to build and deploy the software onto the device for testing. While PC emulators for HoloLens and VR exist, they cannot accurately reflect user interactions due to e.g. the missing natural hand input. Fortunately, there exists a solution for rapidly testing the application directly on the device from the Unity editor for both HL2 and MQ2: Holographic remoting [51] enables wireless streaming of the scene directly to HL2 and sending back input events. The application behaves as if it were run directly on HL2, with the important exception of certain runtime libraries not being accessible while using holographic remoting. For testing certain features (such as room scanning) the application would therefore still have to be deployed onto the device. For MQ2 there exists a similar way of streaming content to it and sending back input events, namely Quest Link [52], which can be used both wired or wirelessly (Air Link).

The versioning of the Unity project is achieved via Git [53].

For the development of the prototypical application, an iterative approach was chosen. The allotted development period of ten weeks was divided into three parts:

- **Prototype V1 - pre-alpha:** 3 weeks development + 1 week evaluation
- **Prototype V2 - alpha:** 2 weeks development + 1 week evaluation
- **Prototype V3 - beta:** 2 weeks development + 1 week evaluation

Each part consisted of two or three weeks of development followed by one week of evaluating the new version.

3.3 Evaluation

The evaluation of the prototypical application consists of three parts:

1. **Demonstrations**

Demonstrating the prototype in its first and second iteration to users in an open, exploratory way and interviewing them about their experience, expectations and ideas

2. **System data tests**

Running technical measurement tests on the final prototype to evaluate different options and variables within the application

3. **Example use case**

Conducting an example use case of the final prototype with users and interviewing them as well as taking technical measurements during usage

The three evaluation approaches will be described in more detail in the following sections.

3.3.1 Demonstrations

After the first and second iterations were finished, the resulting prototypes were each tested by the author and demonstrated to a number of volunteers. As each demonstration required two participants (one in AR, one in VR) the author participated in these demonstrations. Excluding the author, the two iterations were demonstrated to:

- Prototype V1: 1 user
- Prototype V2: 5 users (1 already tested V1)

The users' proficiency with AR and VR ranged from having no experience at all to being experienced VR developers. The demonstrations did not follow a strict procedure, as their purpose was not to create statistically significant data via a questionnaire, but rather to serve as explorations of the technology and its possible uses. During the demonstration, users experienced both the AR and VR side of the application. After each demonstration, an interview of between five and fifteen minutes was held with the user. The author followed an open interview approach to get an impression on the user's experience with the technology pertaining to spatial awareness, avatar

presence and communication, as well as ascertain possible usage scenarios the user could imagine for the application.

3.3.2 System data tests

In addition to demonstrating the application to users and capturing their ideas and input, it was also important to measure certain technical specifications within the application. The purpose of these measurements was:

1. to get an overall impression of the technical performance of the application
2. to optimize certain variables within the application
3. to support or refute claims regarding the user experience

The measurements should serve to answer questions such as the following:

- With what latency are the avatars transmitted?
- Is the avatar transmission smooth or does it stutter?
- How long does it take to transmit a scene with or without chunking?
- When using chunking, how does the chunk grid size influence the transmission time?
- etc.

To answer these questions, certain values were collected during the usage of the application. At this point, the measured values are merely listed. The meaning of these values is explained in **section 4**. The following data were collected where times are measured in milliseconds and transmission size in bytes:

- **Avatar transmission - AR+VR**
 - Time required to serialize and optionally compress the data (when avatar compression is enabled)
 - Time required to transmit the data
 - Transmission size
- **Annotation transmission - AR+VR**
 - Time required to serialize and optionally compress the data (when annotation compression is enabled)
 - Time required to transmit the data
 - Transmission size

- **Full scene transmission - AR only**
 - Time required to compute and retrieve the scene from the API
 - Time required to convert the scene to a serializable object
 - Time required to serialize and optionally compress the data (when scene compression is enabled)
 - Time required to transmit the data
 - Scene vertex count
 - Scene triangle count (triangle indices)
 - Transmission size
- **Chunk scene transmission - AR only**
 - Time required to compute and retrieve the scene from API
 - Time required to convert the scene to a serializable object
 - Time required to slice scene into chunks
 - Time required to sort chunks for ordered transmission
 - Scene vertex count
 - Scene triangle count (triangle indices)

For each individual chunk:

 - Time required to transmit the chunk
 - Chunk vertex count
 - Chunk triangle count (triangle indices)
 - Transmission size

Test design

A testing plan was devised to encompass different states and settings of the prototype application, which could then be analyzed and compared. Several parameters of the application were changed to test how they affected the behavior and performance. The iteration of these variables led to a total of 16 test runs which are summarized in **Table 1**. Tests 1-4 aim to provide a comparison between different avatar transmission intervals and show the effect of avatar compression. Tests 5-7 are intended to show the effect of compression and scene size when the scene is transmitted as a whole. For a chunked scene transmission, tests 8-13 aim to examine the effect of the chunk grid size on transmission times and size whereas tests 11 and 14-16 are intended to show the effect of compression and scene size when transmitting the scene in chunks.

Test #	Transmission mode	Scanning resolution	Chunk grid size [m]	Chunk compression	Scene compression	Avatar compression	Avatar update interval [ms]
1	-	-	-	-	-	Off	0.02
2	-	-	-	-	-	Off	0.05
3	-	-	-	-	-	Off	0.1
4	-	-	-	-	-	On	0.05
5	Full Scene	Fine	-	-	Off	Off	0.05
6	Full Scene	Fine	-	-	On	Off	0.05
7	Full Scene	Unlimited	-	-	Off	Off	0.05
8	Chunks	Fine	0.25	On	-	Off	0.05
9	Chunks	Fine	0.5	On	-	Off	0.05
10	Chunks	Fine	0.75	On	-	Off	0.05
11	Chunks	Fine	1	On	-	Off	0.05
12	Chunks	Fine	1.5	On	-	Off	0.05
13	Chunks	Fine	2	On	-	Off	0.05
14	Chunks	Fine	1	Off	-	Off	0.05
15	Chunks	Unlimited	1	On	-	Off	0.05
16	Chunks	Unlimited	1	Off	-	Off	0.05

Table 1: Test design showing iteration of multiple variables across test runs

Measurements across devices

One of the major complications for the data collection was the measurement across devices. Some of the data points to be collected accrue on the device itself, others are transmission times which need to be collected across devices. What is to be measured in the latter case is the end-to-end delay for a message (avatar, scene transmission etc.) from one device to another. The initial naive approach was to create a measurement and enrich it with metadata on the originating device throughout the measured process, then transmit it along with the payload (avatar, scene etc.) and finalize it on the receiving device (see **Figure 5a**). However, this would not work due to the fact that the clocks of both devices would need to be synced precisely to be able to use timestamps from both devices, e.g. by syncing to an NTP (Network time protocol) or even PTP (Precision time protocol) server in the local network (as e.g. demonstrated by Chao et al. [54]). This was not an option due to the limited networking configuration available on HL2 and MQ2.

A second approach was to send a request for acknowledgment along with the payload and upon receiving the request, the second device would send back a receipt message (see **Figure 5b**). Upon receiving the receipt, the first device would then finalize the measurement using only timestamps from a single clock. In essence, this is how ping works [55]. Ping uses very small packets which are sent back and forth, so

an end-to-end delay time can simply be estimated by halving the round-trip time. In this use case, however, the transmissions are very asymmetrical, as the payload can be quite large, so an end-to-end delay can not be estimated by halving the measured round-trip time. Another problem is potential network congestion. When a large packet (like a scene) is queued to be sent over the network, the blockage can delay measurement receipt messages and thus influence the measurements.

Figure 5: Diagrams of different approaches to measure transmission time

The final approach is to introduce a third device which receives the request and receipt messages from the two headsets (see **Figure 5c**). This solves the synchronization issue, as it only uses the clock from the third device for timestamps. No measurement data have to be sent across the network, except for the small request and receipt messages. Some measurements are taken on the headsets (devices 1 and 2), whereas the transmission times are measured on device 3. The measurement workflows for the different processes can be seen in **Figure 6**. This requires a way to consolidate the data for later analysis, so each process instance (avatar transmission, scene transmission

etc.) receives an ID that is transmitted along with the request and receipt messages. This latency measurement design introduces one deficiency, however: We now have to consider the latencies between devices 1 and 3 as well as between devices 2 and 3. These additional latencies could theoretically also be measured, for example by pinging devices 1 and 2 from device 3. HL2, however, has a very restrictive firewall and will not respond to ping commands. It could be argued that the latencies cancel each other out if the latency between 1 and 3 is similar to the one between 2 and 3. This is only an assumption and cannot be verified without accurate measurements. For this reason, the transmission latencies measured on device 3 are considered low confidence. Values deemed to be of low confidence are highlighted in color in **4.4 System evaluation**. While the numbers may not be precise, they are arguably more or less at a constant offset and can at the very least be used comparatively to show differences between testing runs.

(a) Avatar and annotation transmission

(b) Full scene transmission

(c) Chunked scene transmission

Figure 6: Measurement workflow diagrams for different processes

On-device data collection

The data measurement is directly integrated into the application itself. A helper class called `MeasurementHelper` provides the ability to store both time measurements (using a `System.Diagnostics.Stopwatch`) and arbitrary data (e.g. vertex counts of a mesh) into a dictionary by using the name of the data point as the key and its data as the value. For each process in AR or VR (avatar transmission, scene transmission etc.), an instance of `MeasurementHelper` is created and enriched with data points over time. Each new entry receives an ID (ascending integer) upon its creation, which in combination with the client ID, a GUID (globally unique identifier) created upon starting the application, is a unique process identifier. When a measuring process is finalized, its data points are appended to a list of measurements in the `OnDeviceMeasurementController`. When the application is closed, all measurements stored in this way are converted into csv (comma separated values) formatted strings and written to the device storage as csv files.

Transmission data collection

The transmission data are collected on a third computer, the transmission measurement controller – TMC for short – which receives UDP (user datagram protocol) messages from the two headsets. An exemplary measurement process looks like this: The first headset initiates the transmission process for an avatar update, receives an ID from the `MeasurementHelper` as described above, and transmits that process ID alongside its client ID to the TMC via UDP. The TMC recognizes the message, takes a timestamp and stores a reference to it in a lookup dictionary. When the second headset receives the avatar, it also sends a UDP message to the TMC containing the original process and client ID as well as the transmission size. When the TMC receives this second message, it captures a second timestamp, conducts a lookup search for the process and client ID and if a match is found, finalizes the measurement and removes it from the lookup dictionary. When the application is closed, all finalized measurements are converted to csv and stored as files as described above.

Testing environment

The tests were conducted by the author in their work room and joined kitchen. In preparation for the tests, HL2's cached spatial mapping data were reset via the on-device menu option `Settings > System > Holograms > Remove all holograms`. The author then slowly walked and looked around to build a fresh spatial map of the joined rooms. This took around seven minutes. An overview of the scanned environment can be seen in **Figure 7**, and photographs from different perspectives alongside their scanned representations can be found in **Figure 24** in the appendix. Within the application, the `Flags` class is created to contain all relevant global variables, such as the chunk grid size or whether to use compression or not for a specific transmission type, so they can be quickly changed for a specific test build. The tests were conducted sequentially by building and deploying the Unity project to both devices with the appropriate settings, letting the application run for a little over three minutes, then retrieving the measurements from the three devices (two headsets and transmission measurement controller running on PC) and continuing with the next test. Due to the continuous nature of the scanning process running in the background on HL2, the scene retrieved from the Scene Understanding API is inherently variable. Therefore, the vertex and triangle counts of the scene mesh change across tests. Nevertheless, steps were taken to minimize the variance: No objects within the room were changed during or between the 16 test runs and doors and curtains were kept closed to ensure a self-contained environment.

Figure 7: Bird's eye view of scanned representation of testing environment

3.3.3 Example use case

The system data tests can't yield data pertaining to an average "real-world" use of the application, as there is no interaction between users and the scene is effectively static. Therefore, an example use case was devised to evaluate a more organic use of the application. The author was in AR in the same environment used for the system data tests, while the VR user was in a remote place. Audio communication was realized via an external tool such as a phone or internet call using a hand-free headset. Once both users were inside the application, the author quickly explained the basic use of the interaction tools and then initiated scene transmission. The author then explained that there were two rolled up exercise mats (see **Figure 8**) in their room which should be relocated to a point of the VR user's choosing. The VR user was asked to use the implemented annotation features to spatially communicate their intent. The VR user was also encouraged to direct the author to walk around, thereby expanding the scanned environment to discover a suitable spot to place the mats. This scenario resulted in a natural use of annotations as well as a variable environment, as the virtual world is expanded and modified over the course of the scenario by the AR user exploring previously unscanned areas and moving objects in the real world. When the two mats had been moved, the author then played several rounds of rock-paper-scissors with the participant to demonstrate and evaluate the capabilities of the detailed hand tracking. After the scenario was conducted, the author interviewed the user in the same way as described in **3.3.1 Demonstrations**. During the scenario, the system data were collected as described in **3.3.2 System data tests**. Four users participated in these scenarios. One of them had already tested both previous prototype iterations and another had tested the second iteration.

Figure 8: Exercise mats which are to be stored somewhere else

3.4 Data analysis

The csv files produced by both the on-device and transmission data collection were processed, analyzed and plotted with R [56], a software environment for statistical computing and graphics, using packages from tidyverse [57]. The data collected from the different sources (on-device measurement, transmission measurement) are joined via the combination of process and client IDs. Invalid measurements (such as non-finalized transmission measurements) have been filtered out. All collected data as well as the R scripts required for processing and analysis can be found [here](#) to ensure that the results are verifiable.

4 Iterative development and results

This chapter first goes over the implementation of the prototype application in Unity. For some parts, a basic understanding of Unity, C#, computer graphics and application development in general is assumed. After each development iteration, the feedback users gave on it is presented. This feedback is then processed and results in the next development iteration or, in the case of the final prototype, in an assessment of the example use case. Finally, the results of the technical measurements from the system data tests and the example use case are presented. **Figure 9** gives a high-level system overview of the prototype, showing what systems were implemented in which development iteration. **This video** shows five minutes from an exemplary session of the final prototype application. The complete Unity project including all code can be downloaded [here](#).

Figure 9: High level system overview of final prototype
Systems marked with V2 or V3 were added in the second and third development iteration respectively, systems without a marking in the first

4.1 Prototype V1 - pre-alpha

As there is no user feedback at this point, the feature set of the first prototype iteration is based entirely on the requirement analysis laid out in **subsection 3.1**.

4.1.1 Development

General architecture

A single Unity project is created for the application and the appropriate libraries for HoloLens and AR/VR hand interaction are imported – a full list of utilized packages and their respective versions can be found in **Appendix B**. While some systems like avatar transmission must be present on all platforms, others such as environment scanning should only be active on HL2. Therefore, a separate scene is created for AR, VR and desktop. On application start, the `DeviceDependentContentInjector` determines on which platform/device the application is running and loads the appropriate scene. The AR scene contains all systems relevant for HL2, the VR scene for MQ2. The desktop scene contains everything required for debugging purposes, as it is designed to serve as an intermediary between AR and VR during development. One very important consideration when developing real-time applications is the rendering frame rate. This is especially important for both AR and VR, as low frame rates can induce dizziness and nausea [58]. Since Unity generally works single-threaded, computationally intensive methods run at the risk of a reduced frame rate, as they are executed on the same thread as graphics rendering. Therefore, a system utilizing C# tasks is implemented, which helps to offload expensive computation onto background threads. The different systems mostly communicate by providing access to data via `public event Actions`, which allows other systems to subscribe to receive updates on published data. This enables loose coupling between the systems.

Environment scanning

HL2 generates a spatial map of its surroundings, which is continuously updated and cached in the background while it is turned on and a user is looking and/or walking around. This map can be accessed using Microsoft's Scene Understanding [59], which provides access to the cached environment through a `SceneObserver`. When requesting the environment via `SceneObserver.ComputeSerializedAsync`, a static snapshot

of the current environment state is computed and returned as a `Scene` object. By giving the scene observer different parameters, the data that scene object contains can be controlled. It can contain separate 3D meshes of detected objects, which are categorized into classes such as wall, floor and ceiling. It can also contain quads, which are 2D surface representations of these 3D objects. Additionally, the scene object can contain a world mesh, which is a single large mesh comprising a 3D representation of the entire scanned environment. For the purpose of this prototype, only the world mesh is retrieved from the scene observer. The scene observer can also be configured to retrieve this world mesh at four different preset levels of detail or resolutions – Coarse, Medium, Fine and Unlimited. A visual comparison of the four resolutions is shown in **Figure 10**.

Figure 10: Scanned environment at different scanning resolutions/levels of detail

To control the scanning process during runtime (among other functionality), a floating menu is implemented. The menu generally follows the user at a short distance (using MRTK3's `RadialView`), but can also be grabbed and pinned to a fixed position in 3D space. It contains four buttons to switch the scanning resolution at runtime, as well as a toggle switch to turn the scene computation on and off. **Figure 11** presents an

overview of the menu. Also, see [this video](#) for a short demonstration.

Figure 11: Components of floating menu in AR
A: Scanning resolution switcher, B: Mesh info display, C: MQTT status display, D: Scene computation & rendering toggles, E: Pin/unpin menu, F: 3D manipulator bar, G: Application reset button

MQTT data transmission

Several features, such as scene or avatar transmission, require a network connection. For packet exchange on LAN (local area network), a direct C# socket connection would suffice. As the intended usage scenario for the application is over the internet, however, this would require some kind of NAT (network address translation) traversal or punch-through technique and mediation by some kind of relay server, as the devices can't communicate directly across different networks [60][61]. An alternative for data transmission is the MQTT protocol [62]. While it was originally developed for low-end devices in the IoT (Internet of Things), such as low-frequency sensors, it can also be used as a general-purpose networking solution. MQTT has a publisher-subscriber model, where clients can subscribe to topics (e.g. "an/example/topic") on a broker. When any client publishes to that specific topic, all subscribers receive the published message. MQTT messages have a very small header that contains only a few bytes of metadata, whereas the payload can contain any byte message up to a maximum size of ~ 256 megabytes. One of the main advantages lies in the publisher-subscriber model: Once the transmission has been implemented between a single AR and VR user, the scenario can easily be expanded, e.g. to multiple VR users

who can experience the same environment without any additional implementation. After careful consideration, MQTT was chosen as the communication protocol due to its ease of implementation, inherent multi-user support (one publisher, many subscribers) and the author's previous familiarity with it.

The open source MQTT broker Mosquitto [63] is installed on an Ubuntu server running as a virtual machine. M2MQTT for Unity [64] is used for integration inside Unity, as this library already contains modifications for HL2. A custom MQTT client is implemented by the author that provides the ability to subscribe to and publish JSON-wrapped messages. The JSON wrapper contains metadata, such as a publish timestamp, a client ID (which is a GUID prefixed with the client type, e.g. "AR_73d8217f-fc...") and the message itself, which is another JSON string. Another important MQTT feature are wildcard subscriptions. They are, for example, necessary for avatar transmission if there are more than two clients. You can subscribe to "example/avatar/topic/#" and the "#" acts as a wildcard matching all subtopics such as "example/avatar/topic/AR_1" and "example/avatar/topic/VR_1234". Clients can therefore subscribe to a single supertopic with a wildcard and get callbacks for every other client who is publishing its avatar as a subtopic. When getting such a callback, the information of which client published it (such as "AR_1" or "VR_1234") must then be extracted from the topic. As the M2MQTT library does not offer support for this kind of pattern matching, another solution must be found. There are no publicly available C# libraries for performing this at the time of writing, so it would have to be implemented via custom regular expressions. Fortunately, there exist libraries for performing this task in other languages, such as mqtt-pattern [65], which was written in TypeScript. The relevant methods were converted to C# with the help of ChatGPT [66] (version May24) using the prompt "Convert the following code to equivalent C# code: [...]". The resulting code had to be fixed manually as it was not syntactically correct, but running unit tests on the methods showed that it performed the task of MQTT pattern matching as expected.

Scene transmission & visualization

After scanning the environment in AR, it needs to be transmitted to VR for displaying. The AR user should also be able to visualize the scanned environment directly on HL2 so they know which parts of the environment the VR user can perceive. One of the

main problems for both of these cases is the way in which the environment scanning works: The `SceneObserver` considers HL2 itself as the origin of its coordinate system. As a result, when a scene is captured using `SceneObserver.ComputeSerializedAsync`, the returned scene object originates from the position and rotation of the headset at the moment of capture (see **Figure 12**). Therefore, the headset's pose (position and rotation) in relation to the Unity world origin must be captured at the same moment the scene is captured, so the scene can then be transformed by that offset. In the case of AR on-device visualization, this transformation needs to be performed every frame to correctly position the scanned environment over the real one, as the headset is continuously moving. For transmission, this transformation must only be performed once before transmitting or after receiving. A second problem is the fact that Scene Understanding uses a right-handed coordinate system, whereas Unity uses a left-handed one. This can, however, easily be fixed by converting the coordinates (by inverting the Z axis for the position and the X and Y values for the quaternion rotation). Lastly, for displaying the environment at the correct height in VR, the scanned environment must be offset so that the scanned floor is at Unity origin height ($Z = 0$). This offset is determined by finding the largest floor in the scene by comparing the quad representations' areas and finding the transform of that floor's position relative to the scene origin.

Figure 12: Different coordinate system origins in 3D scene
A: Unity coordinate system origin
B: Scene Understanding coordinate system origin (always at HL2 pose)

A first approach was to directly serialize and transmit the `Scene` object returned by the `SceneObserver`. This would, however, not work, as the Scene Understanding library (`Microsoft.MixedReality.SceneUnderstanding`) was only available on UWP (Universal

Windows Platform), so no code containing any reference to it could be compiled for the Android build for MQ2. As a result, all mesh data must be converted into a custom `SwisScene` object which is used for transmission, and all references to Scene Understanding must be commented out for the Android build via C# preprocessor directives [67]. A new scene is transmitted along with its offset pose and floor pose whenever the former transmission is finished, at a minimum interval of three seconds.

Figure 13: Scene visualization in AR and VR

The scene visualization on AR is realized via a semi-transparent wire frame material and can be turned on and off via the floating menu (see **Figure 11**). In VR, a simple gradient shader (starting at dark gray on the floor and getting lighter towards the top) is used for displaying the scene geometry. See **Figure 13** for a comparison. The desktop scene utilizes the same visualization as the VR scene. Additionally, a saving and loading system is implemented which can serialize and store received environment scans, as well as deserialize and publish them again. Therefore, both AR and VR can be tested independently by using the desktop scene as an intermediary. Stored environments can also be displayed on desktop at a later date for debugging and environment investigation purposes.

Avatar transmission & visualization

For avatars to be correctly positioned in both the real and virtual environments, a common reference point must exist to transform the avatar pose correctly from one coordinate system to another. As already described for the case of scene transmission, this common reference point is determined by analyzing the scene for the largest floor and offsetting the scene, so that the floor sits at $Z = 0$. This results in a common

coordinate system between the real and virtual world which can be used for avatar pose transmission. One deficiency, however, is that this coordinate systems origin slightly drifts around, as it is recalculated every time the scene is transmitted. Because of transmission latency, whenever a new scene is transmitted, there is a window between the computing of a new scene on AR and when it is received and displayed on VR. During this time, AR and VR have different coordinate system origins. This can theoretically lead to jittering avatar poses. As the drift is very small – during testing usually less than 1 cm – this can be solved by slightly smoothing the pose transitions. The avatars are displayed as a floating head and two hands (see **Figure 14**). The positions of the hands are only transmitted when they are actively being tracked. A user's avatar is transmitted continuously at a configurable interval which defaults to 50 ms (which equals a frame rate of 20 fps). It is transmitted as a serialized `SwisAvatar` object containing poses for the head, both hands and whether these are being tracked.

Figure 14: Avatar representation, this is how one user sees another

Hand interactions

MRTK3 provides hand tracking for both AR and VR. While the virtual hands are displayed in VR, they are hidden in AR, as the user can see their actual physical hands and overlaying the virtual hands is neither necessary nor helpful as it would introduce visual confusion. The basic interaction paradigm is the same on both platforms: The primary interaction with the virtual world is the *trigger gesture* which is performed by quickly tapping thumb and index finger against each other, as seen in **Figure 15**. Both hands possess a near interactor for directly interacting, by e.g. grabbing virtual objects with the trigger gesture and dragging them around while keeping their thumb

and index finger connected. The hands also contain far rays with which a user can manipulate far away objects. To reduce visual clutter, the far rays are only active while performing the *pointing gesture* by pointing one's palm actively outward, as shown in **Figure 15**. A ray is shot outwards from the palm and can be used as a pointer. When a user wants to manipulate a far away object, they simply have to perform the trigger gesture while pointing the far ray at the object. See [this video](#) for a short demonstration of the two gestures.

Figure 15: Hands and their interaction gestures

For this first prototype iteration, the only implemented hand interaction is the VR user's movement inside the virtual scene. They can move around by either walking when using room-scale VR, or via teleportation using the pointing gesture at the floor and using the trigger gesture to teleport to the designated spot. In AR, the only interaction is clicking the buttons in the floating menu (see **Figure 11**).

4.1.2 User feedback

The first prototype iteration was demonstrated to a single participant. They experienced both the VR and AR parts. The test was conducted in an environment with extremely low internet bandwidth, high latency and intermittent complete wireless network dropouts, so user acceptance could not be properly tested as the experience was very low-performant and laggy due to the external limitations. One important usability feedback given by the participant was that the avatars when rendered in gray, were not clearly visible, especially in AR. In the tests conducted by the author themselves, the most obvious user experience flaw was identified as distinct rendering lag spikes occurring whenever a scene was transmitted. These lag spikes resulted in disorientation, instable holograms and intermittently frozen avatars every couple of seconds.

4.2 Prototype V2 - alpha

With feedback from evaluating the first iteration, the following improvements were identified as goals for the second iteration:

1. Increase avatar visibility, especially in AR
2. Implement a more stable way of transmitting the scene which doesn't cause lag spikes

Increasing avatar visibility is rather straightforward. The fact that the gray avatar is not well visible on HL2 is due to the way HL2's holographic display works: Black is rendered as transparent, and white is the most opaque color. The brighter a color, the more opaque it is displayed on HL2. Consequently, the avatar color was changed from gray to light blue to ensure better visibility (see **Figure 14**).

Achieving a more stable scene transmission proved more complicated. There were multiple potential optimization approaches. The serialization of the scene data as JSON created a rather large overhead which could be improved with a more efficient serialization method. Compressing the data before transmission to reduce the transmission size was another option. A third approach was to not send the entire scene at once, but slice it into smaller chunks that could be transmitted one after another. All of these approaches were deemed promising and were therefore investigated for the second iteration.

4.2.1 Development

Scene chunking

Slicing the environment into a 3D grid of smaller chunks rather than transmitting it all at once entails several requirements. Being able to update single chunks of the environment without them looking out of place requires a relatively static coordinate system from one scene computation to the next. So, instead of transmitting the offset pose and floor pose along with the environment mesh (as described in **4.1.1 Scene transmission & visualization**), they must both be applied directly to the vertices of the mesh before transmitting it, so the scene position and rotation is "normalized" across scene computations. This increases the computing time on AR but enables a visually smooth chunked transmission, where chunks from different

scene computations fit together well.

There are multiple ready-to-use libraries available for splitting meshes in Unity, such as “Unity Plane Mesh Splitter” (UPMS) [68] or “Dynamic Mesh Splitting” (DMS) [69]. Both of them have drawbacks, however: While UPMS delivers good results, its API expects to work with `UnityEngine.Mesh` objects rather than plain arrays or lists of vertices and triangle indices. As Unity meshes cannot be accessed in any thread other than the main thread (in which graphics rendering happens), using UPMS for splitting larger meshes creates noticeable lag spikes. DMS on the other hand can be used in background threads, but can only split a mesh along a plane into two pieces at a time. Therefore, in order to create a grid, multiple splits would have to be calculated in each axis, for which the library is not optimized. For this reason, a custom mesh splitting solution which is optimized for the use case must be implemented to ensure good performance.

The `MeshSlicer` class contains the method `SliceMeshAsync` which accepts an array of vertex positions, an array of triangle indices and a grid size in meters as inputs. The grid size defines the edge length of the uniform cubes the mesh is split into, see **Figure 16** for examples.

(a) 1 m grid size resulting in $2^3 = 8$ chunks (b) 0.5 m grid size resulting in $4^3 = 64$ chunks (c) 0.25 m grid size resulting in $8^3 = 512$ chunks

Figure 16: Examples of a 2x2x2 m cube split into chunks at different grid sizes

The slicing algorithm works by first determining in which chunk each individual triangle lies and creating a map of these assignments. The position of a triangle is calculated based on its center, which is simply $\frac{vert_1+vert_2+vert_3}{3}$. The algorithm then iterates over each chunk in this map, retrieves all assigned triangles’ vertices and copies them into new vertex and triangle index lists while adjusting the indices to match the new smaller list of vertices. See **Figure 17** for a visual explanation. While each chunk individually is relatively small, the chunking comes at the cost of an increase in total data to be transmitted, because the slicing algorithm inherently

creates duplicate vertices for every vertex belonging to triangles in different chunks. The number of duplicate vertices increases as the chunk grid size decreases due to more triangles being intersected by chunk borders.

Figure 17: Steps of mesh splitting algorithm
Steps are shown in 2D for simpler visualization, but are analogous for 3D

Chunk transmission & visualization

As the total transmission size of the scene increases when transmitted in chunks, there is a need to reduce it in another way. The current serialization of transmitted objects to JSON is great for debugging, as the JSON string is human-readable. It is, however, much larger than it needs to be for simply transmitting the data. Therefore, a new method of serialization is implemented: The object to be transmitted (in this case a `SwisChunk`) is first converted to a byte array with a `BinaryFormatter`. The byte array is then losslessly compressed using a `DeflateStream`. Finally, the compressed data are converted to a Base64 string to be transmitted via MQTT. On the receiving side, the data are decompressed and deserialized to the original object. Preliminary tests show a large saving in transmitted data: As an example, a scene of $\sim 25k$ vertices and $\sim 42k$ triangles went from 2 478 266 bytes as JSON down to 711 347 bytes as a

binary formatted Base64 string, which is a saving of over 70%. However, the reduced data come at a cost of computing time, which increases from ~50 ms for JSON to ~150 ms for the binary formatted Base64 string.

When chunks of different scene scans are displayed next to each other, seams can appear, as the triangles at the borders don't properly fit together. To minimize this visual disruption, the chunks are sorted by all three axes, so they can be transmitted in an orderly fashion as opposed to being transmitted randomly. On the receiving side, each time a chunk is updated, its color is set to light green and then fades back to its original gray color over a few seconds. This results in a 3D scan line effect (**see video**). While this rendering feature was originally implemented as a debugging tool to visualize chunk updates, it improved the visual perception by actively communicating the update process and thus creating a higher acceptance in the users for the visual seams.

4.2.2 User feedback

The second prototype iteration was demonstrated to five participants, one of which had already experienced the first iteration. The participants' experience with MR ranged from having used VR a couple of times before to being active MR developers. All participants experienced both the AR and VR part of the application.

The participants reported an overall smooth experience. The participant who had also experienced the first iteration found the chunk transmission to be much smoother than the former full scene transmission. One participant mentioned that the visual seams created by the chunked transmission weren't bothersome, as the scene itself wasn't completely seamless anyway (because there were always parts missing from the environment). Another participant described both the AR and VR experience as fun: In AR they felt some kind of inherent gamification caused by the scene visualization overlay leading to the urge to scan the room in its entirety to complete the mesh. In VR they were amazed by how few polygons were required to recognize objects they were familiar with.

When asked about problems or improvements, one of the participants said it was sometimes hard to find the other person's avatar and wished for some kind of user interface element (like a compass needle in the heads-up display) for locating them. Three participants wished for more communication features, such as fully animated

hands including the fingers which could be used for intuitive gesture communication, or some tools to annotate the room, such as a laser pointer or movable icons to denote certain places in a room. One participant described the visual representation of the room in VR as a bit bland and wished for a virtual light source around the user for more visual variation in the environment. All participants mentioned that a transmission of scanned colors and a higher resolution in the scanned geometry would improve the experience and offer more possible usage scenarios.

When asked about use cases they could imagine for the demonstrated technology, the participants answered with a wide range of ideas: Several of them mentioned use cases in real estate or building, such as remote viewings or building planning for apartments or houses. Another frequently mentioned topic was remote interior decoration consultation. Two participants named gaming as a potential use case, with simple games like hide-and-seek or more complex procedural games such as escape rooms within the confines of the actual room geometry. Another mentioned use case was social spatial interaction, e.g. for long-distance relationships to experience a shared apartment. One participant also mentioned trainings for search and rescue or similar missions. Finally, one of the participants suggested medical or therapeutic uses of the technology. It could, for example, be used for home consultations as part of occupational therapy to identify problems in an apartment for a patient with reduced mobility or to find out how patients use their hands for certain tasks in everyday life to optimize treatment.

4.3 Prototype V3 - beta

The improvement suggestions mentioned in the user feedback for the second iteration can be summarized to the following topics:

- 1. Better scan quality**

Increase immersion by transmitting not only geometry, but also colors of the scanned environment as well as increase the scanning resolution and lighting.

- 2. Communication features**

Increase the ability of users to communicate by transmitting fully tracked hands, including fingers, and adding tools to communicate spatially via annotations, such as drawing with a laser pointer on a wall or placing icons.

3. Orientation/location features

Add functionality for users to easily find each other when they are lost.

While increasing the scanning resolution would be desirable, the given limitations of HL2 do not allow for it, as the previous iterations already utilized the maximum accessible scanning resolution offered by the Scene Understanding API. The only option would be to implement a custom mapping algorithm using raw sensor data directly (see [29] and [30]). Implementing a custom SLAM or photogrammetry solution is, however, very complex and out of the scope of this thesis. Similarly, transmitting color is possible, as real-time retexturing has already been shown to work for HL1 by Dong and Hollerer [70] [71], as well as commercial products such as “RoomScannerS” [72] or “HoloCameraTextureMapping” [73]. Reproducing their method for use with a current Unity version and HL2 would, however, be very time-consuming and not realizable in the remaining development period. It is nevertheless a very interesting and important feature and should be reevaluated in the future.

Following this assessment, the main focus for the third development iteration was put on communication and orientation features: A detailed hand transmission will enable natural intuitive gestural communication. A hand menu will provide access to different annotation tools such as a “Ping”, which can be used to temporarily direct attention to a certain spot or to oneself, placeable 3D objects to annotate certain spots in a more permanent way, and a laser pointer to enable free-form drawing. These tools are not developed towards a special use case, but rather to demonstrate different interaction methods: Interacting with arbitrary spots directly in the air (Ping annotation), interacting with virtual objects in 3D space (3D object annotation), and interacting with the scanned environment (Laser pointer annotation).

4.3.1 Development

Detailed hand transmission

Transmitting each finger individually instead of only a fixed hand provides a more natural way to communicate spatially, for example by pointing a finger or circling a spot. See **Figure 18** for examples of possible gestures. The `HandsAggregatorSubsystem` is queried for all joints in both hands and they are serialized in the same way as before, together with the head pose into a `SwisAvatar` object, which is then transmitted via

MQTT. The increased power of expression comes at the cost of more data. Where previously only a single pose per hand had to be transmitted, it is now twenty-six: Five per finger, four for the thumb, and one each for palm and wrist [74]. Preliminary tests show that even the increased data are small enough to provide a high-frequency transmission of 20 or even 50 fps, maintaining a smooth experience for users.

Figure 18: Detailed hand transmission enabling more natural gestural communication

Interaction tools & hand menu

Implementing multiple annotation tools into the application requires some kind of selection mechanism. One option for selecting the different tools was by using custom hand gestures, e.g. forming a fist for one tool, a thumbs-up gesture for another and so on. While this selection type might be very quick and intuitive once a user is accustomed to it, the learning curve would be very steep. Another disadvantage is the limited number of recognizable hand shapes, which would limit the number of tools. So a rather traditional hand menu was implemented for tool selection. The menu is usually invisible and only appears when a user looks at the inside of their flat hand (see **Figure 19**). The active tool can then be selected by clicking the appropriate button with the other hand. The selected tool's button is highlighted to indicate that it is active. Whereas teleportation was formerly the only hand interaction in VR, it is now reimplemented as one of the tools. Upon selection, each tool loads its own interaction configuration, which determines whether the far rays are active or not and what action occurs when using the trigger gesture (c.f. **4.1.1 Hand interactions**). See [this video](#) for a short demonstration of the hand menu.

Figure 19: Hand menu in AR and VR

Annotation system

Annotations can be used to mark certain spots in the world or as a method of communication. Each annotation type has a tool which can be selected from the hand menu. The tool can then be used to create annotations of the corresponding type. The three implemented annotation types are explained in more detail in the following paragraphs. Handling annotations for multiple users requires a system for controlling synchronization across devices. The `AnnotationManager` contains methods for creating, updating and removing annotations. When one user e.g. uses the 3D object tool in AR, the AR `AnnotationManager` first creates the object by spawning it in the 3D world and allocates a GUID to it. It then transmits an update message via MQTT to the broker. The annotation update message is received by the VR `AnnotationManager` which checks whether an annotation with the given GUID already exists, in which case it updates its state (position, rotation etc.) or if it doesn't exist yet, spawns a new one instead. Similarly, when a user removes an annotation, it is removed for everyone.

Ping annotation

The primary purpose of the ping annotation is to spotlight a general area or gain attention from other users. The trigger gesture can be used at an arbitrary spot in the air to create a ping annotation. A small semi-transparent pink sphere is spawned at that spot and enlarges over a couple of seconds to visually attract attention (see

Figure 20). While the ping enlarges, it simultaneously is faded out and is automatically removed when fully enlarged. The far rays (c.f. **4.1.1 Hand interactions**) are deactivated while using the ping tool to avoid confusion, as it cannot be used to ping at a distance. See [this video](#) for a short demonstration of the ping tool.

Figure 20: Ping annotation

3D object annotation

The 3D object annotation can be used to mark spots more permanently (they are persistent for the length of a session). When a user chooses the object annotation tool in the hand menu, they can select between different preset objects with arrow buttons (see **Figure 21**). Four object annotation presets have been implemented for the prototype, but this can be extended with minimal effort by any 3D model. A miniature preview of the selected object is displayed floating above the hand and can be spawned into the 3D world with the other hand using a dragging trigger gesture. An object in the world can be repositioned and reorientated anytime by dragging it around. It can also be rescaled by holding it with both hands and performing a two-handed zooming gesture. Each annotation also has a button with which it can be deleted. This deletion button is always rotated towards the user. Users can interact with the object both directly and from a distance using the far rays. See [this video](#) for a short demonstration of the 3D object annotation tool.

Laser pointer annotation

The laser pointer can be used to draw on the scanned environment and floor free-form. While the tool is selected, the user can point the far ray at a spot and move their

Figure 21: 3D object annotation

hand while holding the trigger gesture to draw. The laser pointer works by performing a ray cast along the far rays and moving the laser spot to the point of collision of the ray with the environment. When the laser spot is moved along a surface, it emits particles along its trajectory and creates the drawing. After five seconds, the drawing starts to fade out and disappear. It is not intended to be a permanent marking, but rather a tool to quickly highlight areas or spots across surfaces. See [this video](#) for a short demonstration of the laser pointer tool.

Figure 22: Laser pointer annotation

4.3.2 User feedback on example use case

The third prototype iteration was demonstrated to four participants, one of whom had already experienced the second and one both the first and second iterations. The participants' experience with MR ranged from having used VR only once before to

being active MR developers. All users experienced only the VR part of the application by participating in the example use case as described in **3.3.3 Example use case**. All participants completed the scenario of identifying possible locations to move the mats to and directing the AR user to do so using the annotation tools provided. All participants described the scenario as achievable and the annotation tools as fun and functional.

Three of the participants, one of whom had never used hand tracking before, described the hand interactions as very natural and intuitive. Two also mentioned that it was comparatively easy to learn the hand interactions inside the application, as the avatars induced a sense of togetherness, which made it easy to learn by imitating the author's hand gestures. One participant called the gestural communication enabled by the detailed hand tracking very expressive, especially for rock-paper-scissors, another one described a feeling of having real spatial interactions with another human being. Two participants said they could easily recognize objects and room features. One participant described a feeling of being able to manipulate the real world by using annotations to direct the AR user.

When asked about improvement suggestions, all participants mentioned that both color and higher resolution would facilitate recognition of objects, especially smaller ones (a similar remark to the evaluation of V2). Two participants depicted their visual impressions as standing in a gray, rocky cave as opposed to a room, one brought up the idea of manually placing light sources inside the scene where windows and lamps were to mitigate this. Two participants wished for a fourth annotation type, a placeable sign on which they could type text. One participant mentioned that full-body avatars could be helpful in gaining a better sense of scale, another one asked for a way to measure distances, such as a measuring tape tool. One participant suggested that teleportation should always be available in VR with a separate gesture, as opposed to being only one of the selectable tools.

When asked about use cases they could imagine for the technology, remote viewings, building planning and games were brought up as before during the evaluation of V2. Two participants voiced the idea of a "room share", similar to a screen share, to explain the functionalities and operations of a room or venue to someone who considers renting it in the future, such as an Airbnb apartment, an event location or a stage. One participant mentioned remote consultations for room acoustics as a viable

use case. Two participants named cultural institutions as suitable use cases: Galleries or memorials could develop interactive exhibitions in which remote VR visitors can interact with AR visitors inside the physical exhibition and place annotations.

4.4 System evaluation

In this section, results of the technical measurements taken during the system data tests and the example use case tests will be presented. Values are generally rounded to one decimal place. Byte values are rounded to the nearest integer. Vertex and triangle counts are rounded to the nearest thousand, since it is not the exact count that matters, but rather the order of magnitude. Two common scene sizes occur within the tests: A scene with 24-25k vertices and 41-42k triangles was scanned at the “Fine” resolution setting (c.f. **4.1.1 Environment scanning**) and is considered small. A scene with 109-112k vertices and 195-199k triangles was scanned at the “Unlimited” resolution setting and is considered large.

Values derived from low-confidence measurements, as discussed in **3.3.2 System data tests**, are **colored in orange**. As the vertex and triangle counts inherently vary from scene to scene due to the continuous mapping process running in the background on HL2, these counts were collected along with the timing measurements. That way, they could be normalized later for better comparison. During data analysis, however, the decision was made to use the timing measurements as is without normalization. This decision was motivated first by the desire to keep tables legible and human-understandable by not using complex units such as *milliseconds per 1k vertices*, and second by avoiding to create a false sense of accuracy. The latency timings were already of low confidence and these inaccuracies would possibly have been increased by the process of normalization. The author argues that the measured timings are comparable for the purposes of this analysis because the vertex and triangle count do not strongly fluctuate within each of the two size categories defined above.

The presented data for avatar and annotation transmissions originate from transmissions *from AR to VR*, so serialization/compression time is measured on HL2. Measurements for the transmissions *from VR to AR* are very similar (within a few ms) and are therefore not presented for the sake of clarity. Logically, all data for scene transmissions also originate from transmissions *from AR to VR*, as scene transmissions are uni-directional.

4.4.1 Avatar transmission

The total latency for an avatar (c.f. **Figure 6a**) is similar across the different transmission intervals tested, as demonstrated in **Table 2**. Both the time it takes to serialize the avatar data as well as the transmission time vary within a very narrow margin. Serialization is between 17.2 (SD = 3.8) and 17.8 ms (SD = 6.0), transmission time is between 40.7 (SD = 17.7) and 43.2 (SD = 16.0) ms.

Interval	Serialization _{Mean} [ms]	Transmission _{Mean} time [ms]	Total latency _{Mean} [ms]
20 ms (50 fps)	17.8	43.2	61.0
50 ms (20 fps)	17.2	44.2	61.4
100 ms (10 fps)	17.2	40.7	57.9

Table 2: Avatar transmission process measurements at different transmission intervals

Applying compression (while transmitting at an interval of 50 ms) for the avatar data increases the computing time only slightly, from 17.2 (SD = 5.2) to 18.0 (SD = 10.9) ms. The transmission time also increases slightly, from 44.2 (SD = 20.4) to 44.7 (SD = 45.4) ms, as **Table 3** shows. However, the transmission size drastically decreases from 7 238 (SD = 0) to 3 978 (SD = 228.6) bytes.

Compression	Serialization+ Compression _{Mean} [ms]	Transmission _{Mean} time [ms]	Total latency _{Mean} [ms]	Transmission size _{Mean} [bytes]
Off	17.2	44.2	61.4	7 238
On	18.0	44.7	62.7	3 978

Table 3: Avatar transmission process measurements with and without data compression

Comparing the avatar latencies at different scene transmission conditions (while transmitting the avatar at an interval of 50 ms) in **Table 4** yields interesting results. Transmitting a small scene, either as a whole (row 2) or as chunks at 1 m grid size (row 4), does not seem to influence the avatar transmission very much compared to when no scene is concurrently transmitted (row 1). The median and mean total latency is around 60 ms in all three cases. With a larger scene, this changes significantly. When transmitting the scene as a whole (row 3), the median total latency rises to 68.0 ms while the mean increases even more to 133.1 (SD = 213.1) ms. When the larger scene is transmitted in chunks at 1 m grid size (row 5), the median and mean total latency only rise slightly and are comparable to the values from the smaller scene. For plots visualizing these latencies, see **Figure 25** and **Figure 26** in **Appendix A**.

Figure 25c clearly shows where the much higher mean latency originates from: There are distinct periodic lag spikes approximately every three seconds, which is when the large scene is transmitted. Similarly, when comparing the density plots in **Figure 26**, while all cases are right skewed, the large full scene transmission (case 3) has a much wider spread of values.

Scene transmission	Scene size _{Mean}	Total latency _{Median} [ms]	Total latency _{Mean} [ms]	Total latency _{Max} [ms]
None	-	56.0	61.4	318.0
Full scene	~24k verts, ~41k tris	56.0	63.4	289.0
Full scene	~109k verts, ~195k tris	68.0	133.1	2 646.0
Chunked scene	~24k verts, ~42k tris	59.0	62.3	290.0
Chunked scene	~112k verts, ~199k tris	61.0	67.6	447.0

Table 4: Avatar latencies at different scene transmission conditions

4.4.2 Scene transmission

Table 5 gives an overview of the measured times for transmitting a full scene in one piece (cf. **Figure 6b**). Using compression on a small scene (row 2) increases the total scene latency to 2 354.2 (SD = 78.8) ms compared to 2 044.5 (SD = 66.7) ms when not using compression (row 1). This overall increase is a result of the time required for compression increasing by more than the time required for transmission decreasing, while the time for scene computation and conversion stay about the same. The transmission size on the other hand decreases from 1 496 546 (SD = 3 887.2) to 702 442 (SD = 807.6) bytes. When transmitting a larger scene (row 3), all individual times increase (albeit at different rates) for a total latency of 5 738.7 (SD = 508.6) ms and a total transmission size of 6 902 373 (SD = 3 627.8) bytes.

Compression	Scene size _{Mean}	Scene computing _{Mean} [ms]	Scene conversion _{Mean} [ms]	Serialization+ Compression _{Mean} [ms]	Trans- mission _{Mean} [ms]	Total latency _{Mean} [ms]	Trans- mission size _{Mean} [bytes]
Off	~24k verts ~41k tris	1 262.8	82.8	482.0	216.9	2 044.5	1 496 546
On	~24k verts ~42k tris	1 315.5	80.6	825.8	132.4	2 354.2	702 442
Off	~109k verts ~195k tris	1 781.2	338.4	2 770.3	848.8	5 738.7	6 902 373

Table 5: Full scene transmission latencies with and without compression and different scene sizes
Large scene with compression turned on was not included in the test design, as no significant informational added value was to be expected. The large scene with compression turned off was mainly included to demonstrate increased avatar latencies.

Table 6 gives an overview of the measured times for transmitting a scene in chunks (cf. **Figure 6c**). Scene computation and conversion times are roughly comparable

to the full scene transmission data above, which is to be expected, as the process is identical up to that point. Slicing the scene into chunks takes between 113.9 (SD = 11.9) and 121.6 ms (SD = 10.8) for a small scene and between 443.7 (SD = 31.0) and 458.5 (SD = 53.7) ms for a large scene. The chunk sorting time can be considered negligible, as the mean is below 1 ms in all cases. For a small scene, the times until the first chunk is transmitted and until all chunks (i.e. the entire scene) are transmitted are 1 561.3 (SD = 45.0) and 3 873.8 (SD = 162.5) ms without chunk compression and 1 571.1 (SD = 39.7) and 3 936.0 (SD = 69.0) ms with compression, respectively. The total transmission size (i.e. the combined sizes of all chunks) decreases from 1 754 863 (SD = 8 842.5) without compression to 893 672 (SD = 1 526.2) bytes with compression. For a large scene, turning on compression increases the time until all chunks are transmitted considerably from 6 237.0 (SD = 239.3) to 7 507.9 (SD = 188.4) ms while the total transmission size is reduced from 7 348 610 (SD = 17 083.2) to 3 498 306 (SD = 2 202.3) bytes.

Com- pression	Scene size _{Mean}	Scene com- puting _{Mean} [ms]	Scene con- version _{Mean} [ms]	Scene sli- cing _{Mean} [ms]	Chunk sor- ting _{Mean} [ms]	First chunk trans- mitted _{Mean} [ms]	All chunks trans- mitted _{Mean} [ms]	Total trans- mission size _{Mean} [bytes]
Off	~25k verts ~42k tris	1 317.3	82.2	121.6	0.5	1 561.3	3 873.8	1 754 863
On	~24k verts ~42k tris	1 335.5	79.8	113.9	0.3	1 571.1	3 936.0	893 672
Off	~112k verts ~199k tris	1 716.2	282.2	443.7	0.3	2 486.1	6 237.0	7 348 610
On	~112k verts ~199k tris	1 697.7	280.5	458.5	0.3	2 484.8	7 507.9	3 498 306

Table 6: Chunked scene transmission latencies with and without compression and different scene sizes

An overview of the measured timings at different chunk grid sizes can be found in **Table 7**. Chunk compression was turned on in all cases. Scene computing and conversion are omitted from the table, as they are not variable at different chunk grid sizes. With increasing grid size (and therefore decreasing number of chunks in the scene), the time required to slice the scene decreases from 188.8 (SD = 38.3) ms at 0.25 m to 106.6 (SD = 13.8) ms at a 2 m grid size. Chunk sorting time is negligible overall, with a similar decrease from 4.0 (SD = 2.0) to 0.2 (SD = 0.4) ms. While the time until the first chunk is transmitted is in a narrow band of 1 531.2 (SD = 41.5) to 1 660.5 (SD = 746.4) ms, the time required until all chunks are transmitted decreases drastically from 33 861.4 (SD = 287.3) ms at 0.25 m to 2 715.8 (SD = 62.6) ms at 2 m grid size. The number of transmitted vertices decreases with increasing grid sizes due

to a reduction in vertex duplication (see **4.2.1 Scene chunking**), with $\sim 40k$ vertices at 0.25m to $\sim 25k$ vertices at 2 m grid size. As is to be expected, the total transmission size for all chunks decreases from 2 501 794 (SD = 2 186.6) to 778 821 (SD = 1 225.1) bytes. The avatar latencies vary between 60.6 (SD = 20.6) and 66.4 (SD = 18.4) ms without a clearly discernible pattern. The timings are visualized in **Figure 23**, which clearly shows the increase in total transmission time with smaller grid sizes.

Chunk grid size [m]	Scene size _{Mean}	Scene slicing _{Mean} [ms]	Chunk sorting _{Mean} [ms]	First chunk transmitted _{Mean} [ms]	All chunks transmitted _{Mean} [ms]	Transmitted vertices _{Mean}	Transmission size per chunk _{Mean} [bytes]	Total transmission size _{Mean} [bytes]	Total avatar latency _{Mean} [ms]
0.25	$\sim 24k$ verts $\sim 41k$ tris	188.8	4.0	1 571.7	33 861.4	$\sim 40k$	1 295	2 501 794	66.4
0.5	$\sim 24k$ verts $\sim 42k$ tris	142.1	0.9	1 582.0	10 241.7	$\sim 32k$	2497	1 294 404	64.0
0.75	$\sim 24k$ verts $\sim 42k$ tris	118.1	0.4	1 549.6	5 274.5	$\sim 29k$	4 579	995 972	65.2
1	$\sim 24k$ verts $\sim 42k$ tris	113.9	0.3	1 571.1	3 936.0	$\sim 27k$	7 142	893 672	62.3
1.5	$\sim 25k$ verts $\sim 42k$ tris	110.7	0.2	1 660.5	3 068.5	$\sim 26k$	14 288	814 388	160.0*
2.0	$\sim 25k$ verts $\sim 42k$ tris	106.6	0.2	1 531.2	2 715.8	$\sim 25k$	22 252	778 821	60.6

Table 7: Chunked scene transmission latencies at different chunk grid sizes
 *: This dataset contains several extreme outliers caused by a non-application-related network lag, which distorts the mean. When the outliers are filtered out (1.5 x inter-quartile range), the mean lies at 58.6 ms.

Figure 23: Chunked scene transmission latencies at different chunk grid sizes

4.4.3 System data from example use case

In total, four example use case tests were conducted. Two of them were realized remotely, with the VR participant being in a different place from the author, e.g. in their own apartment. The other two were conducted in the author's apartment, with the VR user being located in a separate part of the apartment. While the experience

was likely nearly identical, as communication was only possible via audio chat in either case, the latter two tests enabled the collection of transmission data as both the AR and VR headset were on the same local network and could transmit their timings to the transmission measurement controller (c.f. **3.3.2 Transmission data collection**). The first of these two tests – EUC01 – lasted for around 22 minutes and used a scanning resolution of “Fine” (c.f. **4.1.1 Environment scanning**) throughout the entire test, whereas the second one – EUC02 – had a duration of approximately 24 minutes and used a scanning resolution of “Fine” for about half a minute before switching to “Unlimited”. During the last five minutes of EUC02, scene transmission was turned off entirely. Both tests were configured with chunked transmission, a chunk grid size of 1 m and an avatar and annotation transmission frequency of 50 fps. Compression was turned on for avatar, annotation and chunk transmissions.

Table 8 gives an overview of the amount of data transmitted during both tests. The data transmitted from VR to AR comprise the avatar and annotation updates. The data transmitted from AR to VR also comprise the avatar and annotation updates and additionally the scene updates. Over the course of test EUC01, a total of ~ 344 mB were transmitted from AR resulting in a data rate of $\sim 271 \frac{\text{kB}}{\text{s}}$ (SD = 123.1), whereas a total of ~ 172 mB were transmitted from VR resulting in a data rate of $\sim 136 \frac{\text{kB}}{\text{s}}$ (SD = 14.8). During test EUC02, a total of ~ 498 mB were transmitted from AR resulting in an increased data rate of $\sim 357 \frac{\text{kB}}{\text{s}}$ (SD = 267.0), whereas a total of ~ 196 mB were transmitted from VR resulting in a data rate of $\sim 141 \frac{\text{kB}}{\text{s}}$ (SD = 18.0), which is comparable to the VR rate of EUC01.

Test	Scanning resolution	Duration [s]	Total transmission size AR → VR [bytes]	Transmission rate _{Mean} AR → VR [bytes/s]	Total transmission size VR → AR [bytes]	Transmission rate _{Mean} VR → AR [bytes/s]
EUC01	Fine	1298	360 774 144	277 946	180 830 518	139 314
EUC02	Fine + Unlimited	1427	521 789 604	365 655	205 540 985	144 037

Table 8: Data transmission during example use case tests

Figure 27 and **Figure 28** in **Appendix A** show the development of the data rate over time: A relatively constant transmission rate on the VR side of both tests is clearly visible, which results from the avatar transmission. A spike in the transmission rate occurs whenever the VR user creates or interacts with an annotation. On the AR side, the transmission rate is more volatile from second to second due to the nature of

the chunked scene transmission, which is not as constant as the avatar transmission. The annotation spikes on the AR side get lost in the noise of the scene transmission, except for the last five minutes of EUC02 where the scene transmission was turned off. When looking at the avatar latencies over time, spikes in EUC02 can be observed while the scene is transmitted at “Unlimited” resolution. However, these spikes were not subjectively noticeable during the test by either the author or the participant.

An overview of the measured latencies during both tests is shown in **Table 9**. The mean avatar latency is 71.0 (SD = 30.9) and 73.2 (SD = 34.5) ms for tests EUC01 and EUC02, which is marginally higher compared to the system data tests. The mean annotation latency is at 84.4 (SD = 38.9) and 85.8 (SD = 44.5) ms, respectively. The time until all chunks for a scene are transmitted is at 6 185.1 (SD = 1 996.2) and 10 940.4 (SD = 3 622.8) ms. This is also higher compared to the system data tests.

Test	Total avatar latency _{Mean} [ms]	Avatar transmission size _{Mean} [bytes]	Total annotation latency _{Mean} [ms]	Annotation transmission size _{Mean} [bytes]	All chunks transmitted _{Mean} [ms]	Total scene transmission size _{Mean} [bytes]
EUC01	71.0	4 010	84.4	1227	6 185.1	947 269
EUC02	73.2	4 008	85.8	1215	10 940.4	3 729 677

Table 9: Latencies for avatar, annotation and scene transmission for example use case tests

5 Discussion

5.1 Interpreting the results

5.1.1 Development

Over the course of three iterations, a working system with which a remote VR user can perceive the physical environment of an AR user has been created. With the first iteration, the basis for scanning, transmitting and visualizing the environment as well as a common coordinate system or frame of reference between the physical and virtual scene was established. This common reference was used to correctly locate the users' avatars in the environment with the intention of enabling a shared spatial awareness. In the second iteration, the scene transmission was improved by slicing the scene mesh into chunks and transmitting them successively instead of the entire scene at once. This greatly increased the application's performance by eliminating lag spikes in both rendering and avatar transmission. In the third iteration, detailed hand transmission enabling complex gestural communication and a set of annotation tools with which users can mark spots in the environment have been implemented.

5.1.2 User feedback

The feedback received from participants during demonstrations helped shape the next iteration. For the second iteration, user acceptance was already very high, as they generally described the application as smooth and a positive experience overall. After testing the third iteration, users again expressed that using the application was fun and that the annotation tools worked very well. Almost all users described a sense of togetherness and feeling present in the environment; one participant even felt like having real spatial interactions with another human being. This means that the goal of shared spatial awareness can be considered met. The detailed hand transmission was mostly described as very expressive and a good form of communication. All participants characterized the hand interactions as natural and intuitive. The participants could easily recognize larger objects such as tables, sofas and chairs, as well as room features like doors and windows, even at reduced scanning resolutions. This greatly helped with gaining an understanding of a room and situating oneself within it. Nevertheless, almost all participants expressed a wish for a better

scanning resolution and color transmission. The look in VR was mostly characterized as functional, but bland and not very appealing.

The participants offered a wide array of ideas for possible use cases, which can be grouped in the following categories:

- **Residential/Construction:**

In the field of real estate, remote viewings could be organized in which an agent scans an apartment or house and potential buyers/renters can explore it at their own leisure without having to travel. Similarly, an apartment could be scanned for remotely planning construction work, such as renovations or reconstruction without the need for an architect or building planner to travel. The application could also be used as a form of “room share” (similar to a screen share) to explain the appliances of an Airbnb apartment to a renter, the operations of a venue to an event organizer, or the spatial characteristics of a stage to a director.

- **Consultation/Therapeutical:**

Remote consultations where the geometry or spatial layout of a room are relevant could also benefit from the application. It could, for example, be used to conduct consultations for interior decoration (where to put a sofa, table or painting) or room acoustics (which walls should receive acoustic elements). Furthermore, a medical professional could assess the spatial arrangement of a room for compatibility with certain movement restrictions or use hand tracking to observe how a patient uses their hands in everyday activities to optimize treatment. The latter is, however, not very practical with the current HL2 hardware, as the frustum in which hand tracking works is limited (hands are e.g. not tracked at hip height while looking forward).

- **Trainings/Simulations:**

Training for search and rescue or similar missions could be performed using the technology. An AR user could e.g. search a partially collapsed building for survivors and mark their positions with annotations, so a rescue team could then be directed to them. The relatively slow scanning process would, however, not make it viable for real missions, at least with the current HL2 hardware.

- **Social/Gaming:**

Possible use cases include simple games such as hide and seek, or more complex procedural games such as escape rooms, or cooperative games that incorporate

physical room topology into gameplay. In private life, the application could be used to virtually invite other people into one's apartment and spend time together. Compared to social VR such as VRChat [75], users could explore an actual physical space instead of a virtual one. It could also be used as a means of experiencing togetherness in a familiar surrounding, e.g. for long-distance relationships.

- **Cultural:**

Galleries or memorials could host interactive exhibitions in which remote VR visitors and physical AR visitors could interact and communicate about the exhibits. VR visitors could annotate the exhibition and AR visitors could manipulate the real world by interacting with the exhibits.

While most of the previously mentioned use cases could be achieved with the existing application parts of AR, VR and desktop, almost all of them would benefit from an increased scanning resolution and color transmission. As the application was not developed towards a specific use case, adaptations would have to be implemented for most of the use cases described above.

5.1.3 System evaluation

Avatar transmission

Avatar latency is about the same for the tested transmission intervals of 10, 20 and 50 fps (see **Table 2**). Therefore, the highest transmission rate of 50 fps should be chosen for the smoothest and most fluid avatar movement. The total latency for an avatar, i.e. the time it takes from one person moving their hand to the other user seeing that motion, is around 80 to 100 ms (~ 20 ms serialization + ~ 40 - 60 ms transmission + ~ 20 ms deserialization), which is well below the acceptable limit of real-time perception [41]. Enabling compression increases the serialization time by less than 1 ms, but decreases transmission size by $\sim 45\%$ (see **Table 3**), so it should be turned on to reduce the data rate without noticeable cost in latency. When looking at avatar latencies while a scene is simultaneously transmitted, large latency spikes are introduced to the avatars whenever a large scene is transmitted in one piece (see **Table 4**). The probable reason for this is network congestion: A large scene packet blocks the transmission queue in the local MQTT client while it is being serialized

and transmitted, and thus avatar packages must wait until the scene is transmitted, resulting in the lag spikes visible in **Figure 25c**. Transmitting the scene in chunks solves this problem, as each individual chunk is small enough as not to block the transmission queue. Interestingly, a bimodal distribution can be seen in some of the density plots in **Figure 26**, with the main peak between 50 and 60 ms and a second smaller peak around 90 ms. It is unclear what causes this distribution.

Scene transmission

While transmitting a scene in one piece is considerably faster than transmitting it in chunks with ~ 2 s vs. ~ 3.9 s (at 1m chunk grid size), the disadvantages strongly outweigh this advantage (compare **Table 5** and **Table 6**). For one, the avatars (and annotations) suffer from periodic lag spikes, as described above. Second, the serialization and deserialization of the entire scene in one go can lead to an unstable rendering frame rate, as some of the required processes (like instantiating the large mesh) can't be executed in a background thread. This results in a sub-par user experience, as a stable, high frame rate is critical for AR and VR headsets [58]. It can also be argued that a higher latency in scene transmission is not detrimental, as it is not perceived as real-time anyway, so a difference between 2 and 4 or even 10 seconds would not necessarily be noticed. Using compression on the transmitted scene chunks increases the time until all chunks are transmitted only slightly for a small scene (~ 60 ms), but noticeably for a large scene (~ 1.3 s), while it reduces the transmitted data by ~ 49 and ~ 52 %, respectively (see **Table 6**). Therefore, using compression on scene chunks is a trade-off between shorter scene update times and a smaller data rate. Depending on the specific use case, both have merit: A smaller data rate is useful for areas with sub-par wireless network coverage, and shorter scene update times can be helpful in scenarios in which objects in the physical world regularly change their positions. The tests presented in **Table 7** and visualized in **Figure 23** show no clear optimum for the tested chunk grid sizes between 0.25 and 2 m – the larger the grid size, the less total data need to be transferred and the faster until all chunks are transmitted. Further tests with different scenes and larger grid sizes are required to find an optimum. The much longer time until all chunks are transmitted for small chunk grid sizes can possibly be explained by the fact that a cubically increasing number of chunks need to be serialized and compressed, and

both the serialization and compression time are not negligible even for very small chunks. Another important factor for testing larger chunk grid sizes is avatar latency. For the tests performed up to a grid size of 2 m, the avatar latencies were all in an acceptable range, but at some point, increasing the chunk size will lead to the same effect described above (transmission queue blocking). All in all, it can be concluded that transmitting the scene in chunks as opposed to in one piece increases the total data rate due to vertex duplication (c.f. **4.2.1 Scene chunking**), which leads to longer transmission times, but provides a much smoother experience overall.

Annotation transmission

The annotation latencies measured during the example use case tests were between 80 and 90 ms, which is a little higher than the avatar latencies, but can still be considered real-time. This means that communication through annotations is as consistent and fluid as via avatar gestures.

Data rates

The data rates measured during two example use case tests, which can be seen in **Table 8** and are visualized over time in **Figure 27** and **Figure 28**, indicate that the application should work well with a relatively low-bandwidth internet connection, as long as the latency to the internet service provider is within an acceptable range. Even with the highest possible scanning resolution of “Unlimited”, the outbound data rate from AR never exceeded $1 \frac{\text{mB}}{\text{s}}$ and averaged at $\sim 360 \frac{\text{kB}}{\text{s}}$. This depends on several factors, such as the chunk grid size and complexity of the environment. However, the data rate will not increase with a larger scanned environment; only the time until all chunks for a single scan are transmitted will. The data rate is a little higher compared to video calling. For example, for a video input of 1280x720 pixels, Zoom has an average upstream of $\sim 100 \frac{\text{kB}}{\text{s}}$, Google Meet of $\sim 122 \frac{\text{kB}}{\text{s}}$ and Microsoft Teams of $\sim 179 \frac{\text{kB}}{\text{s}}$ [76]. These three upstream rates include audio, however, whereas the application prototype does not.

5.2 Limitations

User feedback

The different versions of the application prototype were shown to only seven unique users, most of whom were well versed in using VR. Therefore, user feedback should not be considered representative of a larger potential audience. Also, the demonstrations and subsequent interviews were only loosely guided and did not follow a standardized procedure.

Technical measurements

Some tests, e.g. those for the avatar frame rate, were conducted in isolation from other systems in order to keep the number of tests to a manageable number and limit the influence of co-dependent variables. While the measurements taken are valid in isolation, the systems might interact with each other and produce different results when running the full application.

Most latency measurement means have a very high standard deviation, as the values are spread relatively wide (see **Figure 26** as an example). However, the subjective impression of both the author and the demonstration participants was that the other person's avatar movement was fluid and stable, pointing to a relatively static latency. The high variance in the data might therefore be caused by the process of three-device latency measuring described in **3.3.2 Measurements across devices**. This may further point to a reduced accuracy of the measured transmission latencies in general. As discussed in that section, however, this method of latency measuring was the only viable option for the given combination of hard- and software.

All measured transmission latencies can only be transferred directly to setups where both the AR and VR headset reside in the same network and are in relatively close proximity to each other. Due to the chosen approach to measuring, transmission latencies could not be measured for connections over the internet. Nevertheless, the demonstrations conducted over the internet also show high user acceptance of the encountered avatar and annotation latencies. Additionally, it cannot be ruled out that the performance of the access point, which provided the wireless network for both the AR and VR headset during the testing or the networking hardware in general, had an effect on latency. During some tests, network outages occurred, causing sharp

spikes in latency.

Another potential bottleneck is the MQTT broker, as it was not stress tested to determine a maximum throughput. This is, however, relatively unlikely, as the measured bi-directional data rate of $\sim 500 \frac{\text{kB}}{\text{s}}$ should be well below the limit of the broker's hardware (4 GB RAM, 4 cores @ 3.8 GHz Intel Xeon E3-1275v6).

The process of measuring itself might also introduce additional latency compared to running the application without taking measurements. However, this effect should be small, as the measurement system only takes timings with a stopwatch and sends out small UDP messages.

5.3 Reflection

During the development of SWIS, there were various technical and conceptual hurdles to overcome. One problem arose from using a single Unity project for all platforms. The Scene Understanding SDK was used to retrieve the scanned environment on HL2 as a `Microsoft.MixedReality.SceneUnderstanding.Scene` object. The initial approach was to directly serialize and transmit this scene object so it could be visualized in VR. During the first two weeks of the development, this approach worked, because the AR part was deployed on HL2 and the VR part ran directly from the Unity editor. When trying to build for Android for deployment to MQ2, however, numerous errors regarding the Scene Understanding import were thrown. Building for Android (or Windows x64) did not work as long as there was any reference to `Microsoft.MixedReality.SceneUnderstanding` in any script within the entire Unity project, even when it was not used in the VR scene. The solution was to implement a custom `SwisScene` object into which all relevant data were copied from the `SceneUnderstanding.Scene` object before being serialized and transmitted. Additionally, all code related to Scene Understanding had to be commented out using preprocessor directives [67] to enable conditional compilation for each platform.

Another problem specific to Unity is that most common data types like `UnityEngine.Vector3` or `UnityEngine.Quaternion` are not marked serializable, meaning that they cannot be serialized to a byte array with a `BinaryFormatter`. However, this is necessary to properly compress and transmit the data. Therefore, custom types such as `SerializableVector3`, `SerializableQuaternion` etc. had to be implemented, and data had to be copied to these serializable types before transmission, leading to

structural and computational overhead.

A further challenge was to develop an approach to ownership and authority for the 3D object annotations, as they could be handled by multiple users simultaneously. In a traditional server-client architecture, a client attempting to change the position of an annotation would have to request ownership of that annotation from the server before it could do so. The server would ensure that multiple users could not manipulate the same object at the same time. In this architecture using MQTT, there is no central server authority that manages ownership, as all clients are equal. The solution that emerged from testing was that if multiple users grab the same object, it shoots back and forth between their hands (like a rubber band), and when all users but one let go, the object snaps to the user still holding it.

5.4 Recommendations for future work

The prototype SWIS developed throughout this thesis has been shown to generally work. Nevertheless, there are numerous areas that could be improved. One of the most impactful improvements would be adding color to the virtual mesh by capturing images with HL2's main camera and texturing the mesh by projecting these images onto it. The process has already been shown to work for HL1 [70][71]. This improvement would, however, result in much higher bandwidth requirements. Another major improvement would be an increase in scanning resolution, enabling the recognition of small and delicate objects or features. This could be achieved by implementing a custom SLAM solution with [29] or [30], utilizing the advanced performance of an external computer. While this would help with some use cases that require a higher resolution, it would complicate others through the inconvenience of requiring an external computer.

Instead of updating the entire scene by transmitting all chunks, an update priority system could be implemented. With this approach, chunks in close proximity to the AR user could be updated at a higher frequency than those further away. On one hand, this would introduce more visual seams, as there would no longer be a single updating "scan line", but on the other hand, updates from the real world could be perceived sooner in the virtual world (for example if the AR user moves a piece of furniture).

The chunked scene transmission could be optimized, e.g. by measuring the available

network bandwidth and dynamically adjusting the chunk size and applying compression if necessary. The scene geometry could be simplified by using the quad representations provided by Scene Understanding for areas with a small number of details like flat walls or using a kind of plane fitting as presented by Levoll-Steen [16] to reduce the amount of transmitted data.

There is also room for improvement in the compression, which could further reduce the required bandwidth. Other compression algorithms such as LZMA [77] could be tested for data saving in relation to computing time.

Implementing audio chat directly into SWIS could create an even more immersive spatial awareness. Audio spatialization could be used to make a voice originate directly from the corresponding avatar's position.

Immersion through the avatars could further be experimented on, e.g. by implementing full-body avatars (as opposed to floating hands and head), including inverse kinematics controlling the limbs that are not directly tracked. Jiang et al. present a promising method that includes an estimation of leg movement [78].

There are multiple measures that could be implemented to improve usability. A short tutorial explaining the basic hand interactions could be added to the start of the application, and the hand interactions themselves could be revised: One participant had a problem with "double clicking" (using the trigger gesture would result in two activations), which could be mitigated by implementing a cooldown period for the trigger. Another option would be to have users holding the trigger gesture for a prolonged time for it to be recognized.

Further annotation types like more symbols, text signs or a measuring tool could be added to give users more options for communication. The ability to place virtual light sources could improve the perceived reality of the scene. Another feature that would support other use cases is a system that can store and recall annotations for a specific scene across application sessions. This would, however, require a stable frame of reference across sessions, which could be implemented using spatial anchors [79]. SWIS itself is a general demonstration of the technology, and while it can be used for specific use cases, customization for each use case is advised to meet specific requirements.

5.5 Conclusion

This thesis provided insight into the problem of enabling shared spatial awareness between users in the physical and virtual world. The application prototype developed as part of the thesis was generally shown to solve this problem by scanning the physical environment of a user with an AR headset and transmitting it to a remote VR user. An evaluation of the application showed that seeing each other as avatars within a shared environment facilitates a sense of togetherness and presence in the environment. Furthermore, analysis showed that the application performs well in real-time. Compared to other methods, using only a single standalone headset on either side is much more convenient than using specialized mapping equipment and more immersive than using mobile devices. Future technological advances in headsets such as Apple Vision Pro are likely to deliver improved scanning quality and, therefore, an even more immersive experience. While the prototype application was not developed towards a specific use case, several promising areas of application for the technology in the fields of real estate, building, consultation, culture, training and gaming as well as other forms of social interaction were discussed and should be further explored. In conclusion, this thesis contributed to a better understanding of the requirements for enabling shared spatial awareness, which may be the next step toward greater immersion for spatially separated users.

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Appendix

A Figures

Figure 24: Different perspectives of testing environment and their scanned representations

(a) No scene transmission

(b) Full scene transmission, 24k vertices_{Mean} and 41k triangles_{Mean}

(c) Full scene transmission, 109k vertices_{Mean} and 195k triangles_{Mean}

(d) Chunk scene transmission, 24k vertices_{Mean} and 42k triangles_{Mean}

(e) Chunk scene transmission, 112k vertices_{Mean} and 199k triangles_{Mean}

Figure 25: Avatar latencies over time with varying scene transmission settings
For creating these plots the first ten seconds of each test are being discarded to remove irregularities resulting from application start and the next 180 seconds are displayed.

(a) No scene transmission

(b) Full scene transmission, 24k vertices_{Mean} and 41k triangles_{Mean}

(c) Full scene transmission, 109k vertices_{Mean} and 195k triangles_{Mean}

(d) Chunk scene transmission, 24k vertices_{Mean} and 42k triangles_{Mean}

(e) Chunk scene transmission, 112k vertices_{Mean} and 199k triangles_{Mean}

Figure 26: Avatar latency densities with varying scene transmission settings
 For creating these plots latencies above 450ms have been truncated in order to enable better visual comparison between the density curves. This truncation only affects subplot c as all other cases have max latencies below 450ms. See Table 4 for the numbers.

(a) Transmission rate AR

(b) Transmission rate VR

(c) Avatar latency

Figure 27: Transmission rates and avatar latency over time during test EUC01

(a) Transmission rate AR

(b) Transmission rate VR

(c) Avatar latency

Figure 28: Transmission rates and avatar latency over time during test EUC02

B Software

Unity: 2021.3.20f1

Visual Studio: Community 2022 17.5.3

Relevant Unity packages:

Package name	Version
com.atteneder.gltfast	5.0.4
com.atteneder.ktx	2.2.3
com.eflatun.scenereference	2.1.0
com.microsoft.mixedreality.openxr	1.7.2
com.microsoft.mixedreality.sceneunderstanding	0.6.0
com.microsoft.mrtk.core	3.0.0-pre.14
com.microsoft.mrtk.graphicstools.unity	0.4.0
com.microsoft.mrtk.input	3.0.0-pre.14
com.microsoft.mrtk.spatialmanipulation	3.0.0-pre.14
com.microsoft.mrtk.standardassets	3.0.0-pre.14
com.microsoft.mrtk.uxcomponents	3.0.0-pre.14
com.microsoft.mrtk.uxcore	3.0.0-pre.14
com.microsoft.windows.mixedreality.dotnetwinrt	0.5.2009
com.unity.inputsystem	1.5.1
com.unity.render-pipelines.universal	12.1.10
com.unity.xr.openxr	1.6.0

The complete Unity project including all code can be downloaded [here](#). Inside the Unity project, the C# scripts can be found at *Assets/_Content/Scripts*.

C Data

All collected data as well as the R scripts required for processing and analysis can be found [here](#).